

Analysis of the Competitiveness of Bangladesh RMG Sector Using Porter's Diamond Model

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Abstract

Bangladesh's ready-made clothing (RMG) industry has grown in popularity, competitiveness, and importance to the country's development. This paper uses Porter's diamond model of national competitiveness to analyze the reasons that helped the sector achieve this position. The results indicate that while low cost human resources have significantly aided the competitiveness of the sector under factor conditions, the other three diamond-shaped elements (national demand conditions, related and supporting industries, firm structure, and management) were either inactive or not very so. The study advances the idea that countries can become globally competitive in a sector even if the national diamond is not sufficiently impregnable.

Keywords

Competitiveness, Diamond Model, RMG Sector, Productivity, Firm Strategy, knitwear, Infrastructure

1. Introduction

The ready-made garment (RMG) sector has been one of the major driving forces of the national economy. It is the primary source of export earnings, and solely contributes 84.21% towards total export earnings of the nation (BGMEA, 2020). The sector has also been successful in realizing global competitiveness. According to recent trade statistics, Bangladesh is now the second largest apparel exporting nation after China (WorldTrade Organization, 2019). The economy of Bangladesh grew almost three times over the last decade and almost nine times since 1990 (The World Bank, 2020). Studying the underlying causes is crucial because of the sector's increased significance to the national economy and its success in achieving competitiveness. By using Porter's diamond model of national competitiveness, this research intends to analyze the elements that contributed to its construction of competitiveness in the global arena. The majority of earlier research clearly studied the elements therefore they did not offer a thorough insight of the industry. The goal of the paper is to close the current gap and offer a thorough outlook on the industry.

2. Objectives of the study

- To evaluate Bangladesh's RMG sector's competitiveness using Porter's Diamond Framework.
- To recognize the key elements that Bangladesh's RMG sector needs to sustain and accelerate export-led growth.
- To legitimize issues for fundamental arrangement suggestions for the government assistance of RMG area of Bangladesh.

3. Literature review

3.1 Competitiveness and Competitive Advantage

Competitiveness is the ability to face competition and to be successful when facing competition. Being competitive would mean being able to sell goods that satisfy customer demands (in terms of price, quality, and quantity) while also generating steady profits that allow the business to reach success. Competitiveness can be measured in a number of ways, including:

- Price competitiveness
- Non-price competitiveness
- Unit labor costs
- Labor productivity
- The productivity gap
- Competition in the product market
- The level of capital investment

The term “competitive advantage” has become a buzz word in the world of business management and literatures pertaining to the study of business management, yet a distinguished definition is difficult to de-rive (Anon, 2013; Rumelt, 2003). The term was widely popularized by Porter(1985). He considers competitive advantage to be at the heart of business performance. The study of competitive advantage has been primarily based on two view-points; the market based view and the resource based view. The first perspective emphasizes on the ability to create value according to the requirements of the market or industry (Hill, 1988; Porter, 1980; Porter, 1985). It argues that competitive advantage arises from value, which is derived when benefits to customers surpasses the costs of the offer in a way outperforming the competition (Porter, 1985). On the other hand, the second perspective looks into the unique competencies of a firm that provides an edge over competition (Barney, 1986;Ghemawat, 1986). When these competencies and resources of a firm are com-bined to generate distinctive capabilities to outperform the competition in the market, it is termed as competitive advantage, which leads to superior performance (Johnson, Whittington, Scholes, Angwin, & Regnér, 2014).

Although majority of the studies on competitive advantage have been centered on individual firms, it also has been stretched to national economies. Earlier theories of international trade illustrate that certain nations outperform other nations in trade because of differences in national factor endowments (Hill,2011).

Porter (1990) claims that nations prosper in industries where the national environment favors the creation of competitive advantage. He divided the national environment into four broad attributes: 1) Factor Conditions, 2) Demand Conditions, 3) Related and Supporting Industries, and 4) Firm Strategy, Structure, and Rivalry. These together constitute a mutually interdependent and reinforcing system, termed as the “diamond”. He further argues that the diamond can be influenced by “Government” and by “Chance”. It is important to note that, Porter (1990) believes the national diamond to translate into success when all four determinants of the diamond are strong enough. He contends that flaws in any factor can prevent an industry from gaining a competitive advantage.

Fig 1: Porter five forces in RMG Industry

(Source: Study Tex-Blogger)

The Porter Diamond model is a strategic economic model makes an attempt to explain why one nation-state is more successful than another in a given industry. The model states that four determining factors must be present for an industry to have a national competitive advantage. The Porter Diamond Theory of National Edge, often known as the Porter Diamond Model, describes a country's competitive advantage in the global market.

RMG industry, the major source of export earnings for Bangladesh today, actually resulted from a chain of international events trailing back to the 1950s. During that period, the manufacturing of garment products migrated to Japan from Western Europe and North America, as the latter economies were moving towards hi-tech industries. As the economy of Japan progressed, the second wave started and relocated the production of garment to South Korea, Hong Kong, Singapore, and Taiwan during the 1970s. The third flow shifted the garment manufacturing to China, Malaysia, Indonesia, and Thailand followed by Bangladesh, Pakistan, Sri Lanka, and Vietnam (Ahamed, 2013; Rah-man, 2004). The most important milestone for the RMG industry during the early 1990s was the rise of knitted garment products (Rashid, 2006). An advantage of the knitwear segment was that it was beyond MFA quota restrictions (Ahamed,2013). The European Union's increasing demand for knitwear and supportive incentives from the government of Bangladesh has stimulated the growth of knitwear based RMG in Bangladesh (Ahamed, 2013).

4. Methodology

4.1 Exploring the Bangladeshi Diamond

4.1.2 Factor Conditions

Nations vary in their endowment of factors or resources such as land, labor, and capital (Hill, 2011). Porter (1990) categorizes these factors into five broad segments from an industry perspective:

- 1) Human resources, 2) Physical resources, 3) Knowledge resources, 4) Capital resources, and
- 5) Infrastructure.

According to him, the proportions of the components in the mix differ greatly between industries, and nations do better in those where the national mix of factors complements the mix that an industry seeks. Being a labor intensive industry, human resources remain to be a vital factor for the sector. The garment manufacturing involves relatively low skill tasks (Acevedo & Robertson, 2016), eliminating the need for workers with high or medium skills. Thus, the preferred situation for the industry is easy access to low-cost and less skilled labor force. There is no considerable demand for both physical resources (such as cotton or other fibers to manufacture yarn and fabric) and knowledge resources until and unless the sector integrates backwards (i.e. textile engineering, mechanical engineering, chemical engineering). Although designing can be viewed as a knowledge resource, rather than being delegated to manufacturers, the activity is carried out by in-house designers of major global fashion brands or outsourced to design firms. The capital requisite for the industry is low and a factory can be started with several sewing machines (Seijts, 2006). A country's environment having less capital resources is therefore of less concern. Any industry, including RMG, must take into account infrastructure. The two aspects that have been determined to be essential for the industry are "human resources" and "infrastructure," hence only these two are included in the study that follows.

4.1.3 Demand Conditions

Porter believes that home demand has a considerable influence on competitive advantage, and he presents the composition, the size and pattern of growth, and the internationalization of home demand as three broad attributes of it (Porter, 1990). According to Porter (1990), domestic demand is a primary source of a firm's competition in a given industry. The degree of sophistication and level of local consumer demand are the driving forces for firms to manufacture quality products that meet or exceed consumers' standards at the highest level of efficiency and productivity (Sakakibara and Porter 2001).

Bangladesh was considered a low income nation prior to 2014, when it moved to the lower middle income group (The World Bank, 2016). According to the last household income and expenditure survey, 31.5% of the population lives below the poverty line (The World Bank, 2011). This indicates that about a third of the population struggles to meet their daily necessities. Therefore, it is simply too ambitious to anticipate sophistication and a demanding attitude from such a consumer group. Additionally, the average household spends BDT 1081 on apparel per month in Dhaka, BDT 883 in other metropolitan regions, and BDT 710 in rural areas (PPRC, 2016). The range is from US\$ 8.35 to US\$ 12.72 per month at the standard exchange rate of US\$ 1 = BDT 85. It is not difficult to assess the terrible spending pattern that existed in the past when this situation is taken into account. This provides yet another convincing argument that Bangladesh's RMG sector's competitive advantage did not arise from domestic demand circumstances.

4.1.4 Related and Supporting Industries

The existence of internationally competitive and supportive industries in a nation is an important determinant of the creation and sustainability of competitive advantage. It refers to the national presence of suppliers and related industries that have international standard. One of the most pervasive findings of his study is the tendency for the successful industries within each country to be grouped into “clusters” of related and supporting industries. Porter (1990) argues that specialization leads to the sticky (not easily moveable) location advantages that are the true sources of countries’ sustainable competitive advantage. Highly competitive clustering will drive the focal industry to be more competitive through innovation, upgrading, information flow, and shared technology development (Porter 1998). The relationships among these clusters of industries are critical to the success of a given industry within a nation because “they drive learning, innovation and competitiveness, and are considered to produce the maximum synergies when all requisite institutions necessary to drive learning, innovation, and competitiveness and economic agents are connected” (Rasiah 2009, p. 151). Krugman (1986) argues that, in a particular location, specialization takes place due to three main reasons and these are: resources-driven specialization, economies of scale at the firm level and external economies as a result of local clustering. Related and supporting industries can produce inputs that are critical for innovation and internationalization.

Fig 2: Porter’s Diamond Framework

4.1.5 Firm Strategy, Structure, and Rivalry

Rivalry is the most critical driver of national competitive advantage in an industry (Porter, 1990). Due to intense domestic competition, businesses are forced to expand abroad as their growth is constrained by local markets. Additionally, fierce local competition encourages companies to improve quality, efficiency, and innovation, allowing them to meet or even set new international standards. Additionally, he draws attention to regional variations in management beliefs and claims that these ideologies have a significant impact on strategy development and firm structure. According to "Demand Conditions," the local market for ready-made clothing emerged about 10 years after Bangladesh began exporting clothes to foreign markets. This observation offers compelling evidence that domestic competition had no influence on the development of the RMG industry. Additionally, businesses that cater to international markets have started joining.

As of 2019, there are 4621 export oriented garment factories in Bangladesh (BGMEA, 2020). The factories in Bangladesh tend to be much larger than those in other garment producing countries (Fair Wear Foundation, 2013). This is further supported by McKinsey & Company's (2013) study, which illustrates that countries having more factories, such as India (11,000 factories) and Pakistan (7500 factories), lag behind Bangladesh in apparel exports. Because of the huge production capacity, Bangladesh has a prominent position in the international market.

5. Findings& Discussion

The summary of the findings and the factors affecting the competitiveness of the RMG business in Bangladesh are presented at the beginning of this study. In order to address aspects that are not entirely comprehensible within the Porter's framework, it places these findings within the context of Porter's Diamond as measures of competitiveness and extends into other analytical frameworks outside of the Porter's model.

This study's overarching goal is to evaluate Bangladesh's RMG sector's competitiveness using the Porter Diamond Model. Porter diamond model is used as the theoretical foundation for this study in order to accomplish this goal. Porter's theory states that the home environment's four key characteristics—factor conditions, demand conditions, linked and supporting industries, firm strategy, structure, and rivalry—play an important part.

5.1 The Role of Government and Chance Events

Porter (1990) prefers not to think of the government as a factor in determining national competitive advantage, despite the fact that it is an important part of the national environment. Instead, he views the government as a factor that influences the national diamond. According to him, the government accomplishes this through laws, mandates, and policies that either support or oppose the national diamond. He attributes to chance events like discoveries, scientific breakthroughs, wars, foreign government political actions, and changes in global financial markets.

The government has played a pivotal role in shaping the competitiveness of the RMG sector (Ahamed, 2013; Ahmed, Greenleaf, & Sacks, 2014). In the dawn of the sector, subsidized tariffs on imports of capital machineries and raw materials allowed the sector to develop its industrial infrastructure and remain price competitive (Yunus & Yamagata, 2012).

The following diagram summarizes the findings of this study and provides a contextualized framework of the competitiveness of the RMG industry of Bangladesh-

Fig 3: Proposed competitiveness framework of RMG industry of Bangladesh

5. 2. Critical factors for Competitiveness:

The following are the crucial elements that have been determined from the framework mentioned above for the future viability and competitiveness of Bangladesh's RMG industry-

5.2.1 Human Resources:

The availability of a very big pool of employees at a reasonable price who are capable of carrying out the necessary duties, primarily connected to cutting and sewing activities, has played a significant role in the establishment of the RMG sector in Bangladesh. The sector has, however, had to deal with major shortages of highly qualified people resources as a result of its expansion. Due to a lack of skills, Bangladesh has not been able to fully capitalize on the demographic dividend from its

substantial people resource base. The RMG sector is struggling with a lack of skilled workers, low labor productivity, and a reliance on management professionals and skilled workers from other countries.

In comparison to many other nations, the prices of polo shirts, tee shirts, and pullovers made in Bangladesh are competitive, according to data analysis from the Bureau of Statistics of Bangladesh. The following table compares the prices of three Bangladeshi products (a polo shirt, a t-shirt, and a pullover) with those of several other nations in the EU and US markets.

Table 1: Competitiveness of Bangladesh Apparel products in the EU and USA Markets

Country Name	EU Market			USA Market		
	Polo Shirt	T-Shirt	Pull Over	Polo Shirt	T-Shirt	Pull Over
Bangladesh	3.63	2.10	5.46	3.39	1.70	2.94
China	7.36	2.74	8.00	5.47	2.32	5.70
Indonesia	7.52	4.15	7.01	3.87	2.40	3.53
India	5.33	3.10	6.93	4.37	2.33	3.94
Cambodia	5.02	2.99	6.39	3.25	2.20	3.36
Sri Lanka	7.60	2.71	6.79	6.50	3.46	5.08
Vietnam	6.06	2.68	6.53	4.74	2.94	3.60

(Source: Mohibullah et al. 2016)

Although there are plenty of unskilled labor available but many of them have only basic education and very little training of sector specific on garment production process. One RMG related labor force survey identifies that there are some 40 percent of the workforce lack basic literacy and 23 percent have only primary level education (GOB 2015:247). In particular, the country faces acute shortage of skilled workforces and qualified mid-level management. This is important as the advantage of cheap labor does not last for long and on top of that, “the apparel industry has high-value added segments where design research and development are important competitive factors” (Zeller 2012, 77).

5.2.2 Infrastructure:

A critical factor in determining sustainability is the availability of industry-supportive infrastructure, and Bangladesh's RMG sector has substantial shortcomings in this area. According to McKinsey and Company (2011), “infrastructure is the single largest issue hampering Bangladesh’s RMG industry.” In the World Bank Doing Business Report 2017, Bangladesh ranked 176 in general out of 190 countries and placed at the bottom in getting electricity i.e. 187 (World Bank 2017). For Bangladesh's RMG sector to thrive, a sufficient and continuous supply of gas and electricity as a source of energy is essential. Without sufficient gas allocation, it would be very difficult to grow the RMG industry to satisfy global demand and compete for FDI.

Electricity is the cost-effective alternative energy source needed in the clothing sector. And when compared to other nations that are thought of as Bangladesh's rivals in the apparel sector, the cost of power in Bangladesh is quite low.

Energy cost

Figure 4: Comparison in Energy cost by countries

(Source: BKMEA official site, 2014)

5.2.3 Knowledge Resources:

Most Ready Made Garment manufacturers in Bangladesh use the original equipment manufacturing (OEM)/free on board (FOB) process, with the majority employing the extremely basic cutting and making (CM)/cut make and trim (CMT) process. More functional upgrades like original design manufacturing (ODM) and original brand manufacturing are generally lacking (OBM). The RMG sector in Bangladesh is likewise trailing behind in terms of process development, and manufacturers aren't motivated enough to spend money on cutting-edge technology and management. Process upgrading relates to continuous chain improvement of production process investing in skill development thorough using new technology (machines) or change the line operations implementing lean manufacturing management (Rossi et al. 2014:5) and this is a function that the RMG industry in Bangladesh clearly lacks when it operates. However, it does nothing to boost productivity and produce sustainable growth through the adoption of upgraded technology with high-end products. The expansion of new enterprises in the RMG sector with the typical low-end items may temporarily boost Bangladesh's economy.

5.2.4 Access to Finance:

The high bank interest rate and challenges in obtaining financing are two significant areas where Bangladesh's overall corporate development has lagged. High bank interest rates, inconsistent policy, and barriers to financing all have a detrimental effect on Bangladesh's RMG industry development. Achieving the full potential of the RMG sector's contribution to the national economy is still hampered by the nation's incapacity to reduce commercial loan interest to a single digit, make loans available on buyer's guarantee establish systems to acquire quick access and hassle-free loans, and more. Additionally,

many of the factories in Bangladesh's RMG sector need simple access to affordable financing in order to become compliant and competitive; otherwise, many of them may eventually struggle to exist.

The following table displays recent interest rate trends in the apparel industry-

Table 2: Bank interest rate in different commercial banks in different years

Number	Bank	Year	Rate	year	Rate	Year	Rate	Year	Rate	Year	Rate
1	Government Commercial Banks	2010	13%	2011	13%	2012	15%	2013	16%	2014	16%
2	PUBALI	2010	13%	2011	13%	2012	14%	2013	15.50%	2014	15.50%
3	AB-BANK	2010	13%	2011	13%	2012	16.50%	2013	15.50%	2014	15.50%
4	ISLAMI	2010	13%	2011	13%	2012	13.50%	2013	14%	2014	15.50%
5	THE CITY	2010	13%	2011	13%	2012	14.50%	2013	17.50%	2014	19%
6	PRIME	2010	13%	2011	13%	2012	14.50%	2013	16.50%	2014	16.50%
7	DHAKA	2010	13%	2011	13%	2012	15.50%	2013	15.50%	2014	15.50%
8	DUTCH-BANGLA	2010	13%	2011	13%	2012	14.50%	2013	15.50%	2014	15.50%
9	EXIM	2010	13%	2011	13%	2012	17%	2013	17%	2014	18%
10	STANDARD	2010	13%	2011	13%	2012	17%	2013	17%	2014	17%
11	BANK ASIA	2010	13%	2011	13%	2012	14.50%	2013	15.50%	2014	15.50%
12	BRAC	2010	13%	2011	13%	2012	14.50%	2013	17%	2014	20%

(Source: Bangladesh central Bank, available at <http://www.bangladesh-bank.org/>)

5.2.5 Compliance:

The structural and social aspects of compliance have become crucial for the competitiveness of Bangladesh's RMG sector. Recent terrible industrial mishaps have made Bangladesh's RMG sector extremely vulnerable and the nation is experiencing a severe image crisis. One mishap was the collapse of the Rana Plaza on 24th April 2013, eight-story multiplex housing clothing factories which triggered the loss of 1134 garment workers (ILO 2015). Another was the fire incident in the Tazreen Fashions factory that killed an estimated 112 workers on 24th November 2012 (Manik and Yardley 2012). Due to the widespread coverage these two tragic events received in the media, the industry's serious shortcomings were made clear. In particular, it highlighted some of the numerous structural, managerial, and regulatory shortcomings of Bangladesh's RMG industry.

Additionally, quite a few small factories are still not included in any compliance initiatives. There are a handful of illegal, noncompliant factories that are neither BGMEA or BKMEA members or have company registrations under the Companies Act. These unregistered and non-compliant factories work as subcontractors for individual RMG factories, which are obligated to provide a set amount of goods to international customers at the agreed-upon cheap price and within the agreed-upon time period. These companies need to be located and placed under stringent compliance restrictions by the government's Department of Inspection for Factories and Establishments (DIFE), the BGMEA, and the BKMEA.

From the foregoing discussion, it can be inferred that Porter's "National Diamond" framework, which combines the effects of several causes, offers a good framework for describing the creation and expansion of Bangladesh's RMG business. However, the Porter Diamond model cannot fully account for all of the causes that contributed to its emergence or the current difficulties facing the sector.

6. Conclusion & Recommendation:

According to the study, out of all the national factor conditions, human resources have made a considerable contribution to the sector's competitiveness, whereas infrastructure has actually been a barrier. It's interesting to note that the RMG sector, rather than the supplier and allied businesses, sparked the rise of the former. Moreover, approximately ten years after Bangladesh entered the international market, the domestic market for RMG products expanded. Consequently, the attainment of its competitiveness was unaffected by local competition. However, firm size and managerial approach have somewhat fueled the sector's expansion. This study advances the idea that a country can develop a competitive advantage in a given industry even if all of the national diamond's components are working against it. The implications of this viewpoint can be used to the development of national-level strategies. This can be used as an example by less developed nations to create their own competitive industries.

6.1 Recommendation

The goal of the government should be to foster an environment where businesses can improve their competitive advantages in mature industries by adopting more sophisticated technology and procedures and entering more affluent markets.

A coordinated effort from businesses, industry, and government is required to put the aforementioned policy proposals into practice. The following table offers a roadmap for suggested actions, categorizing them as short, medium, and long term depending on the time range.

Table 3: Suggested time frame (short, medium and long term) for recommended policies

Recommended Policies	Short-Term (need immediate attention: 0-12 months)	Medium-Term (one to three years)	Long-Term (Three years+)
Safe Working Conditions	✓	✓	
Product Innovation and Development		✓	✓
market augmentation		✓	✓
Prioritize Domestic Market	✓	✓	
Access to Finance Improvements	✓	✓	
Promote international investment		✓	✓
Continual Market Access Monitoring	✓	✓	✓
Keeping an eye on factory compliance	✓	✓	✓
Development of forward linkages and adaptation of contemporary marketing tactics		✓	✓
Optimization of the Supply Chain	✓	✓	✓

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